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Research Article

A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY TO DEFINE THE OCCURRENCE OF DIABETES MELLITUS IN HEPATITIS C VIRUS CIRRHOTIC PATIENTS AND RELATIONSHIP OF HEPATIC ENCEPHALOPATHY

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Abstract:

Objectives: The aim of our study was to define the occurrence of Diabetes Mellitus (DM) in Hepatitis C Virus cirrhotic patients and relationship of hepatic encephalopathy in Hepatitis C Virus Cirrhotic patients with diabetes mellitus.

Study design: A cross sectional study.

Place and Duration: This Analytic cross-sectional study was conducted in Community Medicine Department of Holy Family hospital, Rawalpindi for the duration of one year starting from September 2019 to August 2020.

Methodology: The sample size of 100 patients was calculated with 95% confidence level, 9.5% margin of error and taking expected percentage of diabetes i.e. 33.5% in patients of Hepatitis C Virus liver cirrhosis. Non-Probability purposive sampling technique was used to select either gender patients with Hepatitis C Virus cirrhosis and ages ranging from 16 to 60 years. Using non-probability purposive sampling we selected 100 patients with Hepatitis C Virus associated cirrhosis. In our study presence of hepatic encephalopathy was clinically determined and selected patients were stratified as diabetic and non-diabetic according to ADA criteria. The Frequency and percentage of hepatic encephalopathy is use to determine the association of diabetes and their odd ratios. P-value 0.05 was considered significant.

Results: From all selected patients (100) there were 34 females and 66 males. According to age Mean \pm SD was as 44.43 \pm 10.16 years. Among these there were 34 patients of Hepatitis C Virus cirrhosis who were diabetic positive. There were 31 patients who has Hepatic encephalopathy with 91.2% of the diabetic cases 48 patients who has Hepatic encephalopathy with non-diabetic patients with odd ratio of 3.876. P value was 0.016.

Conclusion: Hepatic encephalopathy (HE) is significantly associated with diabetes mellitus. Now Hepatitis C Virus patients should be screened for glycemic level and diabetes to prevent development of hepatic encephalopathy.

Key Words: Hepatic Encephalopathy (HE), Diabetes Mellitus (DM), Neuropsychometric Test, West Heaven Criteria, Hepatitis C Virus (HCV).

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INTRODUCTION:

Hepatic Encephalopathy (HE), an alternating or permanent syndrome of neurological dysfunction, is potentially reversible. The clinical spectrum has a wide variation from asymptomatic to comatose stated. Among the asymptomatic patients, abnormal psychometric tests are the only detectable abnormality [1]. A few signs of hepatic encephalopathy may be seen in about 70% of cirrhotic patients on careful examination while the overt features of hepatic encephalopathy including coma are observable in up to 30% patients who die of end-stage [2,3]. liver disease. Ali et al reported that 3.5% of Pakistani population is infected with Hepatitis C virus; the overall result being the epidemic proportion of cirrhosis in Pakistan [4]. Genotypes 1a, 2a & 2b were found in 10.89%, 13.22% & 6.61% cases, respectively. About 6.1% cases had mixed genotypes [5].

Hepatic encephalopathy, a major neuropsychiatric complication, indicates poor prognosis amongst cirrhotic patients [6,7]. Various pathological factors may result in hepatic encephalopathy and one of the major pathways is increased ammonia production by gut bacteria [8,9]. Autonomic dysfunction (AD) of the gastrointestinal tract leads to altered gut motility, which in turn enhances the duration of exposure to intestinal flora. Autonomic dysfunction and smooth muscle dysfunction leading to gastroparesis and motility disorders are frequently observed among cirrhotic patients and may represent an additional mechanism underlying development of hepatic encephalopathy [10,11]. Diabetes Mellitus is commonly seen in patients with chronic liver disease. Hepatic encephalopathy was present in 50.3% of patients. In all, 118 patients had diabetes mellitus (33.5%). Patients with diabetes mellitus had a significantly higher prevalence (58.5% vs 42.6%; $P = 0.03$) and severity of hepatic encephalopathy ($P = 0.01$) than patients without diabetes mellitus [12].

Nearly 50% diabetic patients have delayed gastric emptying, delayed duodenal transit and sluggish intestinal motility resulting in bacterial over growth [13]. Due to shared pathophysiological mechanism of altered GI motility in diabetes and cirrhosis, it is anticipated that patients having both cirrhosis and diabetes have higher likelihood of hepatic encephalopathy. Frequency of Hepatic Encephalopathy in Hepatitis C Virus cirrhotic patients is 95% in Diabetic and 78% in Non-Diabetic patients [14]. Improved glycemic control in these patients will ameliorate any reversible effect of autonomic dysfunction and this meticulous control of Diabetes in

Cirrhotic patients will have positive effect on overall survival of the patients [15]. Hepatitis C Virus associated cirrhosis is frequently seen in Pakistan. The prevalence has been reported to be 6.2% [16]. Hepatic encephalopathy is a common complication leading to frequent hospital admission. However, the association of diabetes and its complication with the development of hepatic encephalopathy has not been studied in our population.

This study was planned to reveal this important and relevant association with the objectives of determining the frequency of diabetes in Hepatitis C Virus cirrhotic patients and discovering the association of encephalopathy in Hepatitis C Virus cirrhotic patients with Diabetes Mellitus.

METHODOLOGY:

This Analytical cross-sectional study was conducted in the Community Medicine Department of Holy Family hospital, Rawalpindi for the duration of one year starting from September 2019 to August 2020. The sample size of 100 patients was calculated with 95% confidence level, 9.5% margin of error and taking expected percentage of diabetes i.e. 33.5 in patients of Hepatitis C Virus liver cirrhosis. Non-Probability purposive sampling technique was used to select either gender patients with Hepatitis C Virus cirrhosis and ages ranging from 16 to 60 years. Cirrhosis was confirmed with Ultrasonography abdomen and Hepatitis C was confirmed with ELISA.

Patients with active gastrointestinal bleeding (hematemesis and melena), active infections like urinary tract infection, respiratory tract infection or increase white blood cells count ($>11000/mm^3$), renal failure and history of taking sedatives/hypnotics like benzodiazepine, methadone, narcotics were excluded. After taking informed consent, patient's demographic profile including name, age, sex, address was noted. Detailed history and examination were done and presence/absence of Hepatic Encephalopathy was determined. The patients were classified as diabetic and non-diabetic (based on above-mentioned criteria). American diabetes association criteria were used to diagnose DM which mean patients were considered diabetic if they were being treated for Diabetes Mellitus (oral hypoglycemic agents or insulin) or had fasting blood sugar level above 126 mg/dl and/or post-prandial blood sugar level > 200 mg/dL. Hepatic Encephalopathy was diagnosed clinically on presence of any of the symptoms/signs of altered sleep patterns, concentration disorders, irritability, asterixis associated with impaired number connection test (NCT), a validated Neuropsychometric test for

diagnosis of Hepatic Encephalopathy. Test was considered impaired if the time taken by the patient is more than 30 seconds.

SPSS version 20 was used for data analysis. The quantitative variables like age was presented as mean \pm S.D. The qualitative variables like gender, diabetic and non-diabetic, and the Hepatic Encephalopathy in

diabetic and non-diabetic group were calculated as frequency and percentages. The qualitative data was compared by Chi-Square test and odds ratio (OR) was calculated as a measure of association between Hepatic Encephalopathy and diabetes considering $OR > 1$ as positive association. P-value 0.05 was taken as significant for all the analyses conducted.

RESULTS:

The mean age of patients was 44.43 ± 10.16 years. There were 66 (66%) males and 34 (34%) females. In this study the frequency of diabetes was determined as 34% among Hepatitis C Virus cirrhosis patients. Among diabetic patients the frequency of Insomnia was 24 (64.7%) while in non-diabetic patients the frequency of insomnia was 43(65.2%). Day night reversal was present 23 (67.6%) diabetic patients while 35(53%) in non-diabetic patients. Irritability was seen in 26 of the diabetic and 40 of the non- diabetic patients. Among diabetic group, 19 (55.9%) patients had asterixis while in non-diabetic group 10 (15.2%) have Asterixis. Moreover, 31(91.2%) diabetic patients had abnormal Neuropsychometric test while 48 (72.7%) non-diabetic patients had abnormal Neuropsychometric test (Table No 01).

Table No 01: Description of different Parameters in Diabetic Versus Non-Diabetic Patients Regarding Hepatic Encephalopathy

Variables	Diabetics (n=34)	%age	Non-diabetics (n=66)	%age	P-value
Insomnia	22	64.7%	43	65.2%	0.4823
Day Night Reversal	23	67.6%	35	53%	0.1457
Poor concentration	26	76.5%	55	83.3%	0.2036
Irritability	26	76.5%	40	60.6%	0.0563
Asterixis	19	55.9%	10	15.2%	0.0000
Normal Neuropsychometric Test	3	8.8%	18	27.3%	0.0160
Hepatic Encephalopathy	31	91.2%	48	72.7%	0.0160

Hepatic Encephalopathy was found significantly higher in the diabetic patients as compared to non- diabetic patients. 91.2% of the diabetic patients were positive for Encephalopathy. While Encephalopathy was higher in males as compared to females. Binary Logistic Regression was conducted to assess the strength of association between Diabetes in Cirrhotic Patients with Hepatic Encephalopathy. It was used to predict the odds of being diabetic versus different variables (Table II).

Table 2: Binary Logistic Regression of to Assess the Odds of Occurrence of Diabetes Versus Studied Independent Variables

Variables	S.E	Wald	Odds Ratio	95%	C.I	P-Value
Gender	522	882	612	220	1.70	348
Insomnia	698	2.357	343	087	1.34	125
Day Night Reversal	812	4.616	175	036	0.85	032
Poor Concentration	075	4.306	9.304	1.132	76.4	038
Irritability	594	055	1.149	359	3.67	815
Asterixis	624	12.517	110	.32	0.37	000
Neuropsychometric Test	765	681	1.880	420	8.42	409
Hepatic Encephalopathy	665	4.15	3.87	1.05	14.26	0.04

Statistically poor concentration (Yes) was found significantly associated as risk (Odds= 9.3; P-value=0.03) for diabetes. Day night reversal (Yes) was recorded as a risk for being diabetic; found as a significantly (Odds=0.1; C. I= 0.32-0.37; P-value=0.032). Other factors found as risk factors for diabetes included Asterixis and Hepatic Encephalopathy. Hepatic Encephalopathy was found strongly associated (Odds= 4.15; C. I= 1.5- 14.2; P-value= 0.04) as risk with diabetes.

DISCUSSION:

Diabetes Mellitus (DM) is frequent in chronic liver disease and there is an increased association of Diabetes Mellitus with Hepatitis C and hepatic encephalopathy (HE). In our setup such studies are not published and we do not have the updated knowledge of the above-mentioned phenomena. Hepatic Encephalopathy is a serious complication of cirrhosis and is the underlying mechanism of death in 30% of cirrhotic patients. The neuropsychiatric aberrancy of hepatic encephalopathy may be chronic due to underlying portal-systemic shunting or may have an acute precipitating factor. Early identification of precipitating factors and comorbidities is the key to the diagnosis and treatment of this critical condition [17,18]. In Pakistan, cirrhosis is being reported in epidemic proportions in close conjunction with the high prevalence of hepatitis B and C [19,20]. The presence of certain co-morbid conditions especially diabetes mellitus has been reported to enhance the risk of hepatic encephalopathy among cirrhotic patients [21]. The purpose of this study was to establish the frequency of hepatic encephalopathy among Hepatitis C Virus infected cirrhotic patients with and without Diabetes Mellitus. In this study, the average age of patients was 44.43±10.16 years.

In this study the frequency of diabetes was determined as 34% among Hepatitis C Virus cirrhosis patients while in 66% patients the diabetes was not seen. In our study, the odds ratio was calculated as 3.875 (95% CI; 1.053, 14.26) which showed that Hepatitis C Virus diabetic cases has almost four time more chance of developing hepatic encephalopathy as compared to those Hepatitis C Virus cases who do not have diabetes. The exact underlying mechanisms are still undefined but diabetic autonomic neuropathy

&consequent constipation along with impaired ammonia metabolism may underlie the phenomenon [22].

DM also increases the risk of development of hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) among cirrhotic patients [23]. Both DM and HCC have share common associated factors, but association between them is poorly identified. Numerous surveys have demonstrated a significant association between Diabetic Mellitus pathogenesis and prognostic features causing high hepatocellular carcinoma prevalence. Consequently, signifying Diabetic Mellitus is a significant risk factor for the development of hepatocellular carcinoma [24]. According to our findings hepatic encephalopathy was seen in 31(91.2%) of the diabetic patients and in 48(72.7%) of non- diabetic patients. The odds ratio was calculated as 3.875 (95% CI; 1.053, 14.26) which showed that Hepatitis C Virus diabetic cases has almost four time more chance of developing hepatic encephalopathy as compared to those Hepatitis C Virus cases who do not have diabetes. The difference between both groups was significant i.e. (p- value= 0.0160).

In our series for hepatic encephalopathy HE the patients were diagnosed clinically on presence of any of the features of sleep disturbance including insomnia& reversal of day/ night, behavior & mood changes, impaired concentration, or asterixis associated with impaired neuro-psychometric test (NCT). Test was considered impaired if the time taken by the patient exceeds 30 seconds. Among diabetic patients the frequency of Insomnia was 24 (64.7%) while in non- diabetic patients the frequency of insomnia was 43(65.2%). Day night reversal was present 23 (67.6%) diabetic patients while 35(53%) in

non-diabetic patients. Irritability was seen in 26 of the diabetic and 40 of the non-diabetic patients. Among diabetic group, 19 (55.9%) patients had asterixis while in non-diabetic group 10 (15.2%) had asterixis. Moreover, 31(91.2%) diabetic patients had abnormal Neuropsychometric test while 48 (72.7%) non-diabetic patients had abnormal Neuropsychometric test.

The significance of optimal glycemic control among cirrhotic patients cannot be underrated as it is a potential contributory factor to development of, hepatic encephalopathy. Binary Logistic Regression analysis was conducted to assess the association of different factors with diabetes and hepatic Encephalopathy. Factors having p value greater than 0.25 were retained and assessed through binary logistic regression at a significance level of 95%. Different factors were found significantly associated with diabetes including day night reversal, asterixis and hepatic encephalopathy. The results of the current study were in line with the previous study conducted in china [25].

CONCLUSION:

There is a large association among diabetes mellitus and hepatic encephalopathy among patients with Hepatitis C Virus associated cirrhosis.

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